

PAPR Reduction in OFDM using New Hybrid Techniques

Vikas kumar¹, Preeti Sondhi²

^{1,2}M.Tech Scholar, Universal Institute of Engineering and Technology, Lalru, Punjab, India

How to cite this paper: Vikas kumar | Preeti Sondhi "PAPR Reduction in OFDM using New Hybrid Techniques" Published in

International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-5, August 2019, pp.1703-1707,

<https://doi.org/10.31142/ijtsrd27820>

IJTSRD27820

Copyright © 2019 by author(s) and International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development Journal. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)

Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing is a frequency – division multiplexing (FDM) scheme utilized as a digital multi – carrier modulation method. A large number of closely spaced orthogonal sub – carriers is used to carry data. The data is divided into several parallel streams of channels, one for each sub – carriers. Each sub – carrier is modulated with a conventional modulation scheme (such as QPSK) at a low symbol rate, maintaining total data rates similar to the conventional single carrier modulation schemes in the same bandwidth. Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) is a Multi-Carrier Modulation technique in which a single high rate data-stream is divided into multiple low rate data-streams and is modulated using sub-carriers which are orthogonal to each other. OFDM is a “Multi-Carrier Transmission Scheme.” OFDM is a good solution for high speed digital communications. In this the data to be transmitted is spreaded over a large number of orthogonal carriers, each being modulated at a low rate. The carriers can be made orthogonal by appropriately choosing the frequency spacing between them. Orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) is a widely used modulation and multiplexing technology, which has become the basis of many telecommunications fields. Therefore, OFDM is an advanced modulation technique which is suitable for high-speed data transmission due to its advantages in dealing with the multipath propagation problem, high data rate and bandwidth efficiency. OFDM have several attractive features which make it more advantageous for high speed data transmission over other data transmission techniques. These features include

- High Spectral Efficiency
- Robustness to channel fading

ABSTRACT

With the advancement in age and its growing demands, there has been fast production in the field of communication system. Signals, which were sent at the beginning in the analog form, are being sent more and more in the digital form now in these days. For improved transmission, even single carrier waves are being recouped by multi carriers' waves. Multi carrier systems like CDMA and OFDM are now a days being implemented commonly. In the OFDM system, orthogonally placed subcarriers are used to send the data from the transmitter end to the receiver end. Presence of guard band in this communication system deals with the ISI issues and noise is mitigated by larger number of sub carriers. But the large PAPR (Peak to Average Power Ratio) of these signals have some unsuitable effects on the communication system. In this research work we have focused on the OFDM System and have implemented various techniques to reduce the PAPR in the OFDM system so that this system can be used more commonly and energetically.

KEYWORDS: PAPR, BER, OFDM, PAPR reduction techniques

1. INTRODUCTION

With the ever-growing demand of this generation, need for high speed communication has become an utmost priority. Various multicarrier modulation techniques have evolved in order to meet these demands, few notable among them being Code Division Multiple Access (CDMA) and Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM).

- Flexibility
- Easy equalization

But in spite of these benefits there are some disadvantages in using OFDM:

- OFDM signal exhibits very high Peak to Average Power Ratio (PAPR)
- Very sensitive to frequency errors (Tx. & Rx. offset)
- Inter carrier Interference (ICI) between the subcarriers

OFDM have got certain disadvantages also. One of the major disadvantages of OFDM is high PAPR associated with the transmitted signal. Large PAPR leads to both in-band distortion and out of band radiation. It also increases the complexity of the analog-to-digital and digital-to analog converter and reduces the efficiency of the Radio-Frequency (RF) power amplifier used. Therefore, it is useful to reduce the PAPR of the OFDM system. In this paper we are studying different techniques to reduce PAPR in OFDM system.

Fig1. Simple block diagram of OFDM system

2. PAPR

The PAPR is the relation between the maximum power of a sample in a given OFDM transmit symbol divided by the average power of that OFDM symbol. PAPR occurs when in a multi-carrier system, the different sub-carriers are out of phase with each other. At each instant they are different with respect to each other at different phase values. When all the points achieve the maximum value simultaneously; this will cause the output envelope to suddenly shoot up which causes a 'peak' in the output envelope. Due to presence of large number of independently modulated sub-carriers in an OFDM system, the peak value of the system can be very high as compared to the average of the whole system. This ratio of the peak to average power value is termed as Peak-to-Average Power Ratio. An OFDM signal consists of a number of independently modulated sub-carriers which can give a large PAPR when added up coherently. When N signals are added with the same phase they produce a peak power that is N times the average power of the signal. So OFDM signal has a very large PAPR, which is very sensitive to non-linearity of the high power amplifier. In OFDM, a block of N symbols $\{X_k, k = 0, 1, \dots, N-1\}$, is formed with each symbol modulating one of a set of subcarriers, $\{f_k, k = 0, 1, \dots, N-1\}$. The N subcarriers are chosen to be orthogonal, that is, $f_k f_{k'} = D$, where $Df = 1/NT$ and T is the original time period. The resulting signal is given as:

$$x(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} X_k e^{j2\pi f_k t},$$

$$0 \leq t \leq NT$$

PAPR is defined as:

$$PAPR = \frac{\max |x(t)|^2}{E[|x(t)|^2]}$$

where $E[\cdot]$ denotes the expectation operator.

2.1 Effect of PAPR

There are some obstacles in using OFDM in transmission system in contrast to its advantages:

- A major obstacle is that the OFDM signal exhibits a very high Peak to Average Power Ratio (PAPR).
- Therefore, RF power amplifiers should be operated in a very large linear region. Otherwise, the signal peaks get into non-linear region of the power amplifier causing signal distortion. This signal distortion introduces inter-modulation among the subcarriers and out of band radiation. Thus, the power amplifiers should be operated with large power back-offs. On the other hand, this leads to very inefficient amplification and expensive transmitters. Thus, it is highly desirable to reduce the PAPR

3. PAPR REDUCTION TECHNIQUES

3.1 Signal Distortion

A. Clipping & Filtering:

A threshold value of the amplitude is set in this process and any sub-carrier having amplitude more than that value is clipped or that sub-carrier is filtered to bring out a lower PAPR value.

B. Peak Windowing:

Peak windowing reduces PAPRs at the cost of increasing the BER and out-of-band radiation. In peak windowing method

we multiply large signal peak with a specific window, for example; Gaussian shaped window, cosine, Kaiser and Hamming window.

A. 3.2 Signal Scrambling Techniques

B. 3.2 Signal Scrambling Techniques

3.2 Signal Scrambling Techniques

I. Selected Mapping

In this a set of different data blocks representing the information same as the original data blocks are selected. Selection of data blocks with low PAPR value makes it suitable for transmission.

II. Partial Transmit Sequence

Transmitting only part of data of varying sub-carrier which covers all the information to be sent in the signal as a whole is called Partial Transmit Sequence Technique.

III. Interleaving

The notion that highly correlated data structures have large PAPR can be reduced, if long correlation broken down. The basic idea in adaptive interleaving is to set up an initial terminating threshold. PAPR value goes below the threshold rather than seeking each interleaved sequences.

IV. Tone Reservation (TR)

The main idea of this method is to keep a small set of tones for PAPR reduction. This can be originated as a convex problem and this problem can be solved accurately.. Tone reservation method is based on adding a data block and time domain signal. A data block is dependent time domain signal to the original multicarrier signal to minimize the high peak.

V. Tone Injection (TI)

It is based on additive method for PAPR reduction. Using an additive method achieves PAPR reduction of multicarrier signal without any data rate loss. It uses a set of equivalent constellation points for an original

3.3 Coding

A. Block Coding

The fundamental idea is that of all probable message symbols, only those which have low peak power will be chosen by coding as valid code words for transmission.

B. Pre-coding

In pre-coding method, modulated data is multiplied with shaping matrix before the formation of OFDM symbol. This type of technique utilizes the positive feature of the

frequency selective multipath channel of OFDM system. In this first the input data is modulated in baseband using modulation scheme like M-PSK, M-QAM etc. The baseband-modulated data stream is transformed by pre-coding matrix. Different methods like pulse shaping function, discrete cosine transformation (DCT) matrix, Hadamard matrix, Zadoff-Chu sequence, generalized chirp-like (GCL) sequence etc. are used to generate pre-coding matrix. After that these pre-coded data are transmitted through IFFT and generate OFDM symbols. Each element of pre-coding matrix should be carefully designed, so that it can reduce the PAPR. Since, we are multiplying modulated data with predefined pre-coding matrix, there is no need of handshake between transmitter and receiver.

4. PROPOSED WORK

In this pre-coder will be combined with scrambling technique and the system performance will be compared. SLM, PTS, DCT can provide good performance for PAPR reduction, and this improvement requires a high computational complexity. Several techniques have been proposed based on low-complexity SLM techniques. SLM requires the transmission of several side information bits for each data block. These bits must generally be channel-encoded because they are particularly sensitive to the error performance of the system. This increases the system complexity and transmission delay, and decreases the data rate. In this work, a VLM pre-coded SLM and combination of DCT with SLM and HADAMARD with SLM techniques has been proposed to reduce the PAPR in OFDM signals. Combination of pre-coding and scrambling techniques reduce PAPR much more as compare to other techniques.

5. DCT SLM TECHNIQUE

The main idea of the proposed scheme is to use a combination of two appropriate methods. One is the DCT matrix transform technique and the other is the SLM technique. The transmitter block is showed in Figure 3. We call this scheme is scheme 1. In the transmit end, the data stream is firstly transformed by DCT matrix, then the transformed data is processed by the SLM unit. If data block passed by DCT matrix before IFFT, the autocorrelation coefficients of IFFT input is reduced, then the PAPR of OFDM signal could be reduced.

In this we use DCT matrix after SLM to further reduce the PAPR of signal. We call this scheme as scheme 2. In his fashion, the autocorrelation of the signal, which has been processed by SLM, is reduced by DCT matrix transform. The PAPR of fine output signal is further reduced. The block of transmitter is showed in Figure 4.

Fig.3 Diagram of proposed SLM scheme1

Fig. 4 Diagram of proposed SLM scheme2

6. HADAMARD SLM TECHNIQUE

In this technique to reduce the occurrence of the high peaks compared to the Simplified SLM. The idea to use the Hadamard Transform is to reduce the autocorrelation of the input sequence to reduce the peak to average power problem and it requires no side information to be transmitted to the receiver. In the section, we briefly review Hadamard Transform. We assume H is the Hadamard Transform matrix of N orders, and Hadamard matrix is standard orthogonal matrix. Every element of Hadamard matrix only is 1 or -1. The Hadamard matrix of 2 orders is stated by

$$H_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$Y=HX$$

The coming input data stream is firstly transform by the Hadamard Transform then the transformed data stream is applied as input to IFFT signal processing unit.

The signal processing step is below:

1. The sequence X is transformed by Hadamard matrix, i.e. Y=HX
2. Apply inverse IFFT i.e y=IFFT (Y)
3. The equivalent SFBC encoding operations in the time domain for generating candidate signal sets is performed, where one with the lowest maximum PAPR is selected for transmission.

The block diagram of Hadamard SLM is shown below.

Fig. 5 Block diagram of Hadamard SLM

7. CCDF OF PAPR

The cumulative distribution function (CDF) is one of the most regularly used parameters, which is used to measure the efficiency of any PAPR Technique. The cumulative distributed function (CDF) of the signal is

$$F(z) = 1 - \exp(-z)$$

The complementary cumulative distributed function (CCDF) is used instead of CDF which helps us to measure the probability that the PAPR of a certain data block exceeds the given threshold.

$$P(PAPR > z) = 1 - P(PAPR \leq z)$$

$$= 1 - F(z) N$$

$$= 1 - (1 - \exp(-z)) N$$

8. RESULT & DISCUSSION

From the above graph, it can be seen that the value of PAPR in original OFDM signal is 10.85dB.

The above graphs gives the value of PAPR in Hadamard Transform OFDM signal is 7.5dB.

The above graph shows that the value of PAPR in Discrete Cosine Transform OFDM is 5.69dB.

The above graph shows that the value of PAPR in VLM Precoded SLM scheme is 5dB

Table No. 5.1 shows comparison between ofdm, hadamard ofdm, dct-ofdm, vlm precode slm ofdm on the basis of PAPR

Techniques	PAPR value in db
Original OFDM	10.85db
Hadamard transform OFDM	7.5db
Discrete Cosine Transform OFDM	5.69db
VLM precoded SLM technique OFDM	5db

In this paper a survey on PAPR reduction techniques has been discussed. This is concluded that scrambling techniques give good performance but it needs side information for receiver to recover original data block, also it increases complexity. Pre-coding based techniques result good with no need of side information and works with less complexity. Hybrid technique pre-coding plus scrambling give best result for PAPR reduction.

References

- [1] Agarwal, A., Behera, C. and Agarwal, K. (2013) "Effect of Guard Time on BER Performance of OFDM based WiMAX (IEEE 802.16d) System," International Journal of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Volume 6, Number 1, 2013.
- [2] Ahmed, H. A., Sulyman, A. I. and Hassanin, H. S. (2009) "BER Performance of OFDM system with channel Impairments," The 9th IEEE International Workshop on Wireless Local Networks (WLN 2009), October 2009 20-23.
- [3] Arundash, A. and Gagri, V. (2006-2010) "OFDM system and PAPR reduction techniques in OFDM systems", Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering National Institute of Technology, Rourkela.
- [4] Aulakh, S. K. and Sheetal, A. (2012) " Bit Error Rate analysis of Wimax based OFDM system using different constraint lengths of convolution encoder," International journal of research & Innovation in Computer Engineering, Vol 2, issue 2, April 2012.
- [5] Awon, N. T., Rahman, Md. M., Islam, Md. A. and Islam, A. Z. M. T. (2012) "Effect of AWGN and Fading (Rayleigh & Rician) channels on BER performance of a Wimax communication system," International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security, Vol. 10, No. 8, August 2012.
- [6] Bakshi, H. and Shirvani, M. (2009) "Peak To Average Power ratio reduction by combining Selective Mapping and Golay complementary sequences," IEEE, 2009.
- [7] Bhardwaj, M., Gnagwar, A. and Soni, D. (2012) "A review on OFDM: Concept, Scope and its Applications," IOSR Journal of Mechanical and Civil Engineering (IOSRJMCE), Volume 1, Issue 1, May-June 2012.
- [8] Park, M., Heeyong, J., Cho, J., Cho, N., Hong, D., & Kang, C. (2000). PAPR Reduction in OFDM Using Hadamard Transform. In IEEE international conference on communications (Vol. 1, pp. 430–433).
- [9] Baig, I., & Jeoti, V. (2011). A new DHT precoding based Interleaved-OFDMA uplink system with improved PAPR for 4G cellular networks. Journal of Engineering Science and Technology (JESTEC), 6(6), 685–694.
- [10] Baig, I., & Jeoti, V. (2013). A ZCMT precoding based multicarrier OFDM system to minimize the high PAPR. Wireless Personal Communications, 68(3), 1135–1145.
- [11] Sun, E., Yi, K., Tian, B., & Wang, X. (2006). A method for PAPR reduction in MSE-OFDM systems. In Advanced information networking and applications, 2006. AINA 2006. 20th international conference on (Vol. 2, p. 4).
- [12] Baig, I., & Jeoti, V., (2010) DCT precoded SLM technique for PAPR reduction in OFDM systems. In 2010 international conference on intelligent and advanced systems (ICIAS) (pp. 1–6).
- [13] Yuan-Pei, L., & See-May, P. (2003). BER minimized OFDM systems with channel independent precoders. IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing, 51(9), 2369–2380.
- [14] Ciochina, C., Buda, F. and Sari, H. (2006) "An analysis of Peak Power Reduction techniques for Wimax systems," IEEE, 2006.
- [15] Dey, M. R. and Islam, M. S. (2012) "Performance Analysis of PAPR reduction for OFDM- BPSK, -QPSK and - QAM using forward error correcting code," 7th International Conference on Electrical and Computer Engineering, 20-22 December, 2012.